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Variability of hmF2 over San Vito: Comparison with International Reference Ionosphere (IRI) Model Predictions

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

A mid-latitude station was selected for this study to investigate the variations in the diurnal and seasonal median values of the height of the peak electron density of the F2-layer of the ionospheric region. Namely, San Vito (SAN)(40.60N,17.80E). Data were arranged into seasons as follow: December Solstices (November, December and January), March Equinox (February, March and April), June Solstices (May, June and July) and September Equinox (August, September and October). The diurnal and seasonal mean values were calculated, recorded and used in the analysis and comparison, this is the basis of this study. Two distinct solar activity periods were considered: 2001-2002 and 2007-2008 which were high solar activity (HSA) and low solar activity (LSA) periods respectively. Observed values were analysed and compared with predicted values of the International Reference Ionosphere (IRI-2007) model, using the two options of CCIR and URSI. The diurnal and seasonal patterns of the observed values are predicted fairly well by the IRI-2007 model, though; there were overestimations and underestimations at different times of the day for both solar activity periods in all the seasons considered. The CCIR option of the IRI-2007 model performed better in the analysis of the predicted values, though, both the CCIR and URSI gave hmF2 values closed to the observed ones for the solar activity periods considered.

Keywords: IRI-2007 model, CCIR, URSI models.

INTRODUCTION

The values of the height of the peak electron density of the F2-layer (hmF2) are predicted periodically by the International Reference Ionosphere (IRI). It releases models for these predictions based on experimental observations of the ionospheric plasma either by ground or in-situ measurements. Two options are available for the predictions: the Comite Consultative International des Radio Communication- CCIR coefficient(CCIR-1991) and the Union Radio-Scientific Internationale- URSI coefficient (Rush et al, 1984). These provide descriptions of mean conditions that should be investigated to estimate their deviations from the observed real ionospheric parameters' values. Observed values of the hmF2 were obtained from the Space Physics Interactive Data Resources (SPIDR), a World Data Center, based in Boulder. Of significance are the latitudinal positions and the solar cycle spread of the data used (Forbes et al, 2000; Fortiadis et al, 2004). The accurate knowledge of ionospheric parameters like the hmF2 is very important to the further advancement and improvement of telecommunications and radio propagations (Lillenstein and Blelly, 2002). HmF2 values help in the determination of the angle of antennae elevations in point-to-point communication. (Sethi et al, 2008).

Many studies had been done on the comparison of the predicted values of the of the hmF2 of the IRI models to the to the observed values at low and equatorial latitudes during both low and high solar activity periods (Wang et al,2009; Zhang et al,2007; Pandey et al,2003). Results revealed that the IRI models' predictions are good for both low and high solar activity periods. However, there were exceptions for the equatorial latitudes during high solar activity where the model did not yield similar post-sunset peaks; a significant feature of equatorial regions. A few discrepancies were also reported for the low latitudes in the studies.

The diurnal and seasonal variations of the observed values of the hmF2 over SAN VITO (SAN) (40.60N, 17.80E) are therefore studied in this work. The values were analysed and compared with the predicted values of the IRI-2007 model in order to understand the predictability of the model at the mid-latitude station.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The data used for this research were obtained from the Space Physics Interactive Data Resources (SPIDR) (<http://spidr.ngdc.noaa.gov>), a resource of the World Data Centre in Boulder. Hourly median values of hmF2 for December Solstice (DEC SOLS) (November, December, January), March Equinox (MAR EQUI), (February, March, April), June Solstice (JUN SOLS) (May, June, July) and September Equinox (SEP EQUI) (August, September, October), have been used for this study. The International Reference Ionosphere (IRI) 2007 model values used for this study were obtained from <http://ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov/models/index.php>.

For the clearer observation of the variations of the hmF2 during the different levels of solar cycle, data from 2001-2002 (which is close, to the peak of the solar cycle), with an average sunspot number R_z of 111.0 and 119.0 respectively to represent a period of high solar activity (HSA) and 2007-2008 with an average sunspot number R_z of 7.5 and 2.9 respectively, to represent a period of low solar activity (LSA), were obtained for analysis. These observed values of hmF2 are compared with values predicted by the IRI 2007 model, using the CCIR and URSI coefficients. To calculate the differences the hourly mean of the observed values and the predicted values, the equation below was used:

$$d = (x - y)^2 \quad (1)$$

Where x = observed values and y = predicted (CCIR or URSI) values.

The root mean square (rms) error between the IRI-2007 (CCIR and URSI) models results and the observed values of the hmF2 was also analyzed, according to the following equation.

$$\text{RMS error} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{24} d_i}{24}\right)} \quad (2)$$

Where d_i represents differences of the observed and predicted values and Σ means summation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diurnal and seasonal variation of hmF2

The diurnal and seasonal variations of hmF2 values during high solar activity (HSA) (2001-2002) and low solar activity (LSA) for SAN (40.6°N, 17.8°E) are presented in Figure 1a and b. The result shows that the monthly median values of hmF2 are higher during HSA period for all seasons. Temperature variations cause hmF2 to increase with increasing solar activity (Rishbeth, 1964). Increasing solar activity raises thermospheric temperature, thus causing thermal expansion which lifts the pressure level at which hmF2 is situated. Thus, the height of F2 peak depends on the temperature profile in the thermosphere (Rishbeth, 1993). For all the months considered for this study, hmF2 has lower values during daytime compared with night time values. This might be caused by the meridional winds, because they produced a strong upward drift at night and a downward drift during the day (Kohl and King, 1967). Diurnal variation of hmF2 is significantly influenced by the following: ion production rate, temperature variations, thermospheric neutral winds and electromagnetic drifts (Fejer, 1997, Rishbeth and Garriot, 1969). The hmF2 values decrease during 0300-1200 UT after which it starts to increase gradually until it reaches its maximum value around midnight, during 0100-0300 UT, Figures 1a and b. The midday minimum is observed between 1100 and 1300UT. The diurnal pattern of the observed median hmF2 values has peaks occurring characteristically between 2400 and 0100 UT. The hmF2 has minimum around midday. This is seen for both HSA (2001-2002) and LSA (2007-2008) period.

Comparisons with IRI-2007

Figures 2a and b and 3a and b show the comparison of the observed hmF2 with those of the IRI-2007, using both CCIR and URSI coefficients. There is a reasonable agreement between the observed hmF2 and the predicted values during HSA and LSA periods. During the HSA period (2001-2002), the observed pre-noon minimum occurs between 0600 and 0800 UT. For the LSA period (2007-2008), the observed pre-noon minimum values occurred between 0800 and 1200UT. The height of the F2 peak falls because of the rapid production of ionization in the lower F region, and reaches minimum before noon (Rishbeth and Garriott, 1969). The CCIR and URSI coefficients predicted accurately the observed pre-noon minimum at Rome. The two coefficients predicted accurately the observed midnight maximum

at 0100UT for DEC SOLS, MAR EQUI and JUN SOLS, the observed pre-noon minimum lies between 0700 and 0100UT and the predicted values are between 0600 and 0100UT. The midnight maximum for MAR EQUI, JUN SOLS, SEP EQUI and DEC SOLS occurred at 0000 and 0200UT, that is the predicted values show that the midnight maximum lies between 0000 and 0200UT in all the seasons. For all the seasons' simulations in SAN the observed pre-noon minimum occurred between 0600 and 1000UT and the predicted values occurred between 0700 and 1000UT. Also, the observed midnight maximum occurs between 0000 and 0100UT and the predicted values show that the midnight maximum lies between 0000 and 0100UT. For JUN SOLS 2007-2008, the observed values were higher and lower than the predicted values at different times of the day. SEP EQUI 2007-2008 had maximum during the day and minimum during the night.

Seasonal Predictions Errors

Tables 1a and b show the calculated percentage errors in the predicted values to the observed one. Apart from the inaccuracies observed in the predictions of maximum and minimum hourly values, errors can also be observed in the variations of the hmF2. MAR EQUI, had the lowest errors, like 13.74% (CCIR)/11.95% (URSI) for 2001-2002 and **13.93 %**(CCIR)/ 13.95% (URSI) 2007-2008. SEP EQUI predictions had the highest errors: 65.45% (CCIR)/ 64.78% (URSI) for (2007-2008). However, there were no observed values for comparison for JUN SOLS for 2001-2002.

CONCLUSION

This study had examined the variations in observed and predicted values of the hmF2. It was achieved by analyzing the diurnal and seasonal averages of HSA (2001-2002) and LSA (2007-2008) hmF2 values for San Vito (SAN) (40.6°N, 17.8°E) in comparison with those predicted in the IRI-2007 models. There is a very close similarity in the pattern of the daily maximum and minimum values. There were few exceptions to this pattern. However, there are discrepancies between observed values and the IRI-2007 predictions using CCIR and URSI coefficients. IRI model underestimates and overestimates the values of hmF2 at different times of the day for all the seasons, during the different solar activity periods considered. There are great variations between the observed values and the IRI-2007 model predictions, for low solar activity. Both the CCIR and URSI options of the IRI-2007 model gave hmF2 values close to the ones measured, the CCIR gave more accurate predictions than the URSI results.

a

Fig.1. Diurnal variations of observed median values of hmF2 during high solar activity (a) and low solar activity (b) periods for San Vito.

a

SAN VITO 2001-2002	%CCIR	%URSI
DECEMBER SOLSTICES 2001-2002	15.96765	15.93854
MARCH EQUINOXES 2001-2002	13.73731	11.95411
JUNE SOLSTICES 2001-2002	N/A	N/A
SEPTEMBER EQUINOXES 2001-2002	16.11276	16.14528

b

SAN VITO 2007-2008	%CCIR	%URSI
DECEMBER SOLSTICES 2007-2008	27.89048	27.8511
MARCH EQUINOXES 2007-2008	13.92585	13.94831
JUNE SOLSTICES 2007-2008	28.28383	29.40975
SEPTEMBER EQUINOXES 2007-2008	65.45216	64.78366

Table 1. Percentage errors in the predicted values of hmF2 during high solar (a) and low solar activity (b) periods to the observed values for Rome.

b

a

b

a

b

a

REFERENCES

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